

GAS, COAL, FUEL

C3MR LNG PROCESS OPTIMIZATION: AN ENVIRO-ECONOMIC STUDY

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Abstract

Since the global energy requirements are expected to rise and the world-wide energy demand is still supplied mostly by fossil fuels, a search for a suitable transition fuel is a high priority. The natural gas is considered the cleanest fossil fuel and is commonly recognized as the best option. However, because the natural gas is usually extracted at remote locations, suitable means of transport are vital in the gas industry. Liquefied natural gas (LNG) is suitable for long-distance transport and is already one of the pillars of secure energy supply in many countries. In this work, a 3.5 MTPA propane-precooled mixed-refrigerant (C3MR) LNG plant is modeled in Aspen Plus and subjected to a robust dual-objective optimization using the genetic algorithm (GA/NSGA-II) and a novel Aspen Plus – Matlab interface. For the optimization study, 18 process variables were chosen and varied in a $\pm 75\%$ interval. Thanks to the novel optimization interface, up to 1000 optimization individuals and 500 generations could be used. To choose the most suitable individual from the 1000 individuals in the final Pareto front, four decision making methods: Euclidean distance, fuzzy non-dimensionalized distance, and two statistical methods have been used and the results have been compared and discussed. The optimization results document approx. 76 mil. USD/year decrease in the total annual processing costs and an over 76 KTPA decrease in the carbon dioxide emissions. Furthermore, the in-optimization behavior of parameters was studied: only 6 out of 18 parameters underwent significant changes throughout the process while the others converged to optimum in the first iterations. Finally, the results of the dual-objective optimization were confronted with the single-objective ones. The conclusion is that dual-objective optimization should be generally favored as the single-objective optimization yields only marginal decrease in the respective objective function while significantly increasing the other one.

Introduction

The energy-intensive industry accounts for 33% of the anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions worldwide¹ and for two thirds of emissions in Europe². In a response, the European Union committed itself to reducing the CO₂ emissions by 80%–95% by 2050³. However, global energy requirements are expected to further increase by 56% between 2010 and 2040⁴ and because the use of renewable resources is still under development, it is expected that 76% of the world-wide energy demand will be still supplied by fossil fuels until 2040⁵. These predictions initiated the search for a suitable transition fuel to bridge the gap between conventional fossil fuels and renewables.

Natural gas is an attractive candidate amongst the conventional sources of energy because of its low carbon emissions and high heating value. These attributes make it the cleanest fossil fuel with the lowest contribution to climate change^{6,7}. Therefore, natural gas is expected to outperform coal as an energy source by 2035⁸. However, natural gas is usually extracted at remote locations. In Figure 1 there are 157 most important gas fields located world-wide: most of the fields are located in the Gulf of Persia and Iran, continental Russia, and former Soviet republics such as Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, continental United States, and in the seas of Australia and Indonesia. While pipeline transport is still prevalent, the transport of the natural gas in its liquefied form is undergoing substantial development. The reason for this is that liquefied natural gas or LNG is suitable for long-distance transport and is generally considered safer than pipeline transport. Furthermore, it enables countries such as the United States to trade gas with Europe. Therefore, it is expected to surpass pipeline transport by late 2020s⁹. However, natural gas liquefaction is a very energy-intensive process (Table I) and comes with a considerable carbon footprint.

The actual situation regarding the natural gas liquefaction can be seen in Figure 2 which displays location and capacities of 42 most important LNG facilities around the world. When compared with the locations of the gas fields, it is only understandable that most of the facilities are located in the Gulf of Persia, on the coast of the United States and around Australia and Indonesia. Russia with only two liquefaction facilities relies mainly on the pipeline transport nowadays but a number of new projects are planned for the upcoming years.

Table I
Specific energy consumption of various LNG technologies¹⁰

Technology	Specific energy consumption / kJ kg ⁻¹
Cascade	1180-1390
SMR	1240-1490
C3MR	1050-1370
Single N2 expander	2370-3450
Double N2 expander	1420-2020

Figure 1. Most important natural gas fields

Figure 2. Most important LNG facilities

There are several LNG technologies, however, the APCI C3MR LNG technology developed by Air Products and Chemicals, Inc. is the most used one. At the moment, it produces more LNG than all other technologies combined¹¹. The Air Products and Chemicals, Inc. is responsible for almost three quarters of the world-wide production, followed by ConocoPhillips, Royal Dutch Shell plc., and Linde plc. Therefore, in this study, the C3MR APCI LNG technology was chosen as the object of study.

Simulation framework

The APCI C3MR LNG Process stands for Air Products and Chemicals' propane pre-cooled mixed-refrigerant natural gas liquefaction process. The process consists of two cycles – the propane cycle and the mixed-refrigerant cycle. The pre-treated natural gas (NG) which enters the system at approximately 25°C and 60 bar is first pre-cooled in the propane cycle to approximately -33 °C. It then enters the mixed-refrigerant (MR) cycle where it is liquefied at approximately -139°C and its pressure is drastically decreased to 2 bar which causes the natural gas to subcool to approximately -160°C.

A more detailed layout of the process is displayed in Figure 3. Propane in the precooling cycle is compressed in a four-stage compressor and condensed in an air-cooler. Then, it is sequentially expanded and partially evaporated thus cooling the NG and MR. Compressed MR, after partial condensation in the precooling section, passes through a flash drum and enters the coil-wound heat exchanger. Here, its liquid part is subcooled to approximately -127°C and expanded in a throttling valve. The vapor is cooled to -139 °C and liquefied, and subsequently expanded in a throttling valve. Finally, MR vapors are collected and compressed in a two-stage compressor.

The described system was modelled in Aspen Plus software for production of 3.5 MTPA LNG or processing of 160 kg/s of natural gas which is a standard capacity of a single C3MR LNG train.

Figure 3. APCI C3MR process flow diagram.

Optimization study

The presented process is very energy-intensive, and the associated carbon footprint is also substantial. Even though the exact figures differ depending on the utilized technology, the liquefaction process accounts for 30–40% of LNG cost¹². Contrary to other studies which set specific or total energy consumption, annualized profit, period of return, or various efficiencies as the objective function¹³, this study uses levelized processing cost as the first objective function because it provides a single number which encompasses CAPEX, OPEX, and the plant economic life. Environmental objectives are not usually incorporated in optimization studies of LNG processes, although, in this study, carbon footprint is calculated as the second objective function based on the total energy consumption and the associated marginal emission factor. However, with lowering of the capital expenses and consequently the levelized costs, the operational expenses typically increase. Also, the total energy consumption increases which causes the carbon emissions to increase. The objectives are therefore conflicting, and a dual-objective optimization needs to be executed. To minimize the two objectives, 18 process parameters were optimized. These parameters are listed in Table II.

Table II

Optimization variables

Parameter	Range
Precooling cycle	
Propane mass flow / kg s^{-1}	$110.7 \leq \dot{m}_{\text{C3-11}} \leq 774.7$
K101 discharge pressure / bar	$1.1 \leq P_{\text{C3-2}} \leq 4.4$
K102 discharge pressure / bar	$1.3 \leq P_{\text{C3-5}} \leq 8.9$
K103 discharge pressure / bar	$1.8 \leq P_{\text{C3-8}} \leq 12.6$
K104 discharge pressure / bar	$3.75 \leq P_{\text{C3-11}} \leq 25.0$
TV104 discharge pressure / bar	$1.1 \leq P_{\text{C3-22}} \leq 2.3$
Mixed refrigerant cycle	
MR mass flow rate / kg s^{-1}	$75.5 \leq \dot{m}_{\text{MR-11}} \leq 528.2$
K201 discharge pressure / bar	$4.4 \leq P_{\text{MR-16}} \leq 30.6$
K202 discharge pressure / bar	$16.3 \leq P_{\text{MR-18}} \leq 113.8$
TV202 discharge pressure / bar	$1.1 \leq P_{\text{MR-11}} \leq 5.3$
E201 outlet temperature (NG) / K	$140 \leq T_{\text{NG-6}} \leq 150$
E201 outlet temperature (MR, l) / K	$140 \leq T_{\text{MR-8}} \leq 150$
E201 outlet temperature (MR, g) / K	$140 \leq T_{\text{MR-9}} \leq 150$
E202 outlet temperature (MR) / K	$130 \leq T_{\text{MR-10}} \leq 140$
Mixed refrigerant composition	
Propane / mass fraction	$0.0868 \leq x_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8} \leq 0.6076$
Nitrogen / mass fraction	$0.0181 \leq x_{\text{N}_2} \leq 0.1269$
Methane / mass fraction	$0.0620 \leq x_{\text{CH}_4} \leq 0.4338$
Ethane / mass fraction	$0.0831 \leq x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_6} \leq 0.5817$

In summary, the optimization problem consists of 2 conflicting objective functions and 18 process parameters. Because traditional optimization techniques such as sequential quadratic programming or similar would not be able to solve such system, the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II) was used. What this algorithm does is that it creates a variety of combinations of parameter values that are called individuals. The algorithm created 1000 combinations and evaluated the processing costs and carbon emissions for each of the combinations (or individuals). The best combinations were kept, the worst discarded, and the rest was combined so that a new 1000 combinations was created. This process was repeated 500 times. Because such process is extremely exhausting and time-consuming, a novel Parallel Genetic Algorithm Interface (PAGAN)¹⁴ was used.

Results and discussion

Results of the optimization, i.e., all combinations based on the processing costs and carbon emissions are displayed in Figure 4. The so-called Pareto front consists of the top 30% of combinations which gave the lowest values of objective functions. To choose the best solution from the 300 Pareto-optimal solutions, four decision-making techniques were utilized: the Euclidean-distance, the normalized distance, the linear programming technique for multi-dimensional analysis of performance (LINMAP), and the technique for order performance by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS). First, the Euclidean distance calculates the distance from a fictive point consisting of the lowest values of both functions. However, this method provides biased results as the objective functions do not reach values of the same order of magnitude. Also, this method assesses both objectives as equally important and provides no statistical evaluation. By employing fuzzy normalization, the effect of different orders of magnitude is erased. However, even though the result is more objective, neither this method provides any statistical evaluation. LINMAP and TOPSIS methods utilize different method of normalization and statistical weights of individual objective functions. These methods assess the distance of solutions to the best and worst weighted normalized points and rank the solutions according to their performance scores.

From Figure 4 it is evident that different methods consider different values as the best solutions. While geometric methods favor minimizing of the levelized costs, statistical methods favor minimization of the carbon emissions. The final choice of the exact parameters must be done based on experience. According to the current situation, however, considering the TOPSIS solution is strongly recommended.

Figure 4. Dual-objective optimization results. Enclosed figure: Pareto-optimal results and their respective distance from zero, non-dimensionalized by fuzzy normalization.

Table III summarizes the actual values of process parameters as well as the results chosen by each of the decision-making techniques. In the first column there are base-case values of the process parameters. In the other columns there are optimized values of the respective parameters.

Table III
Optimized process parameters

Parameter	Dual-objective					Single-objective	
	Base case	Absolute distance	Fuzzy norm.	LINMAP	TOPSIS	min(PC)	min(G_{CO_2})
Precooling cycle							
Propane mass flow / $kg\ s^{-1}$	442.7	446.0	446.1	446.2	446.1	445.8	448.6
K101 discharge pressure / bar	2.500	1.851	1.903	2.437	2.433	1.526	2.532
K102 discharge pressure / bar	5.100	3.761	3.801	4.012	4.007	2.933	4.631
K103 discharge pressure / bar	7.200	6.470	6.684	6.803	6.802	5.739	7.438
K104 discharge pressure / bar	14.30	14.73	14.72	15.00	15.01	14.36	15.05
TV104 dis. pressure / bar	1.300	1.230	1.258	1.510	1.539	1.100	1.715
Mixed refrigerant cycle							
MR mass flow rate / $kg\ s^{-1}$	301.8	291.2	291.2	291.5	291.5	290.1	291.1
K201 discharge pressure / bar	17.50	30.59	30.58	30.59	30.59	30.63	30.56
K202 discharge pressure / bar	65.00	74.74	74.68	74.55	74.55	75.76	73.31
TV202 dis. pressure / bar	3.000	4.987	4.970	4.992	4.992	4.639	5.250
E201 outlet temp. (NG) / K	146.0	142.8	142.8	142.9	142.9	141.4	145.9
E201 outlet temp. (MR, l) / K	146.0	147.2	147.2	147.4	147.4	147.1	146.6
E201 outlet temp. (MR, g) / K	146.0	149.0	149.0	149.0	149.0	149.3	147.4
E202 outlet temp. (MR) / K	134.0	139.4	139.4	139.4	139.5	140.0	130.0
Mixed refrigerant composition							
Propane / mass fraction	0.3472	0.3204	0.3205	0.3207	0.3208	0.3198	0.3200
Nitrogen / mass fraction	0.0725	0.0733	0.0733	0.0733	0.0743	0.0736	0.0731
Methane / mass fraction	0.2479	0.2375	0.2376	0.2384	0.2370	0.2378	0.2377
Ethane / mass fraction	0.3324	0.3688	0.3686	0.3676	0.3679	0.3688	0.3692
Results							
Processing costs / $USD.t_{NG}^{-1}$	146.0	128.1	128.3	130.8	131.0	126.9	143.7
CO_2 emissions / $t.h^{-1}$	70.35	60.98	60.88	60.10	60.07	63.22	58.56
Decrease against base case							
Processing costs / %	-	-12.26	-12.12	-10.41	-10.27	-13.08	-1.575
CO_2 emissions / %	-	-13.32	-13.46	-14.57	-14.61	-10.14	-16.76

Total decrease in processing costs reached 10 to 12%. At the same time, a 13 to 14% decrease in the carbon dioxide emissions was achieved. To further compare the results, a single-objective optimization, aimed either on lowering the processing costs or the carbon emissions, was carried out. Unsurprisingly, when aiming solely on the processing costs, these can be lowered slightly more although the decrease in carbon emissions would be lower. This aspect of the single-objective optimization is even more evident when aiming only on the carbon emissions. While these could be theoretically lowered by almost 17%, the associated processing cost would be lowered much less, by only 1.5%. It can be therefore stated that the single-objective optimization yields only marginal decrease in the respective objective function while significantly increasing the other one and so the dual-objective optimization is favored.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the achieved decrease in processing costs can be roughly translated into 76 million dollars per year in savings. The associated carbon footprint of this process can be potentially lowered by approximately 76 thousand tons of carbon dioxide per year. Furthermore, dual-objective optimization was proven to be superior to single-objective one.

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